

Data Science Life Cycle from Microsoft Azure Perspective

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

We have heard and read a lot about how machine learning algorithms work. That's cool, exciting and motivational but when it comes to putting them into production, we barely find well-defined materials or even well-defined methodologies or frameworks. This is because there are few companies who can successfully transform a research project into a solid AI product. During my career, I've worked with several large organizations who have armies of talented data scientists who research on cutting-edge solutions. The question that I constantly receive from them is how we can make this transformation less painful and more agile. In Microsoft, we built native tools that are to help the whole data science lifecycle from research to deployment to become easier and faster.

2. Aim

To equip data scientists with a native data science stack that eventually drives more agility and higher productivity.

3. Material and methods

TBD.

4. Results

N/A

5. Conclusions

N/A

6. Keywords

Microsoft Azure; Machine Learning Workbench; Azure Model Management Service

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